

“Weeds Biodiversity of Irrigated and Unirrigated Fields of Washim District, Maharashtra, India”

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Abstract

Weeds are undesirable plants that compete with crops for essential resources such as nutrients, water, light, and space, thereby reducing agricultural productivity. Weed management is particularly challenging in species possessing underground rhizomes due to their high regenerative capacity. Although the flora of the washim district was documented by Deore (2010), no comprehensive weed survey had been undertaken in the region over the past sixteen years. The present study was therefore conducted to update and document the weed diversity of the district.

A systematic field survey was carried out from 2020 to 2025 in irrigated and unirrigated agricultural fields across different talukas of Washim District. A total of 210 weed species belonging to 140 genera and 37 families were recorded. The genus *Ipomoea* was found to be the most dominant, while Poaceae emerged as the largest family with 38 species. Unirrigated fields were mainly dominated by *Parthenium hysterophorus*, *celosia argentia*, *Xanthium strumarium*, *Boerhavia erecta*, *Euphorbia geniculata*, *Acalypha* spp., and *Phyllanthus* spp. In contrast, irrigated fields showed dominance of *Anagallis arvensis*, *Dinebra retroflexa*, *Melilotus alba*, *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Digera muricata*, *Moorochloa eruciformis*, *Launea procumbens*, and *Sonchus* spp. The study provides updated baseline information on weed diversity that will support effective weed management and future ecological studies in the region.

Keywords: Agricultural weeds, Floristic survey, Washim District, Poaceae, Weed management

Introduction

Weeds are establishing themselves in agricultural and non-agricultural habitats where they interfere with crop growth by competing for vital resources, leading to reduced yield and quality. Due to their high ecological adaptability, weeds are able to survive under diverse environmental conditions and

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are distributed across almost all climatic zones of the world. Among different weed categories, perennial weeds are particularly problematic in agriculture because of their persistence, vegetative reproduction, and ability to regenerate from underground structures such as rhizomes, making their management difficult.

Washim District is located in the eastern part of Maharashtra and covers an area of 5,095 km². The district is predominantly agricultural, with a major portion of the land under cultivation and a smaller area under forest cover. District comprises six talukas: Washim, Malegaon, Risod, Mangrulpir, Karanja, and Manora. The terrain is largely plain, with parts of the Ajanta Hills extending through the northern and central regions. The natural vegetation of the region is mainly dry deciduous forest.

The present study was undertaken to systematically document the weed flora of irrigated and unirrigated agricultural fields of Washim District, Maharashtra.

Material and Method

Weed specimens were collected from various localities within the study area, and field observations were recorded at the time of collection. These included habit, habitat, flower colour, fragrance, presence of latex, underground parts, plant height, local names, uses, and frequency of occurrence. Each specimen was assigned a unique field number.

Collected plants were processed using standard herbarium techniques, including drying and pressing. Identification was carried out with the help of standard taxonomic literature such as *The Flora of the Presidency of Bombay* (Cooke, 1903, 1908), *Flora of Maharashtra State* (Sharma et al., 1996; Naik, 1998), and other relevant floras (Singh et al., 2001; Singh and Karthikeyan, 2001).

Identified weed species were arranged family-wise according to the classification of Bentham and Hooker. Within each family, genera and species were listed alphabetically, and relevant information on local names, habitat, distribution, and collection locality was documented.

Observation

Table 1: A=Abundant, C=Common, F=Frequent, O=Occasional, R=Rare.

Sr. No.	Name of Species	Family	Local Name	Habitat	Distribution	Locality
1	<i>Cocculus hirsutus</i> (L.) Diels	Menispermaceae	Vasanvel	Unirrigated field	C	M.pir

2	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Papaveraceae	Pivla Dhotra	Unirrigated field	O	Wanoja
3	<i>Rorippa indica</i> (L.) Hiern	Brassicaceae	–	Irrigated field – Wheat, chickpea	C	Ladegaon
4	<i>Brassica juncea</i> (L.) Czern.	Brassicaceae	–	Irrigated field- Wheat	O	Rithad
5	<i>Brassica campestris</i> Linn. Var. Sarson	Brassicaceae	–	Irrigated field- Wheat	O	Wanoja
6	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	Cleomaceae	Pivtilwan	Unirrigated fields	C	Hiwara Bk.
7	<i>Portulaca quadrifida</i> L.	Portulacaceae	Chival	Irrigated fields- Soybean, Tur.	O	Kheda abai
8	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	Portulacaceae	–	Irrigated fields- Chickpea	C	Vilegaon
9	<i>Abelmoschus moschatus</i> Medik.	Malvaceae	Kasturi bhendi	Bunds of fields	O	Sawarkhed
10	<i>Abelmoschus ficulneus</i> (L.) Wight. & Arn.	Malvaceae	–	Bunds of fields	C	Washim
11	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.) Sweet.	Malvaceae	Petari	Bunds of fields	C	Khapardari
12	<i>Abutilon pannosum</i> (G. Forst.) Schldtl.	Malvaceae	–	Irrigated fields- Cotton	C	Washim
13	<i>Hibiscus lobatus</i> (Murr.) Kuntze	Malvaceae	–	Bunds of fields	O	Pimpalgaon
14	<i>Hibiscus cannabinus</i> L.	Malvaceae	Ambadi	Irrigated fields- Soybean, Cotton.	O	Rithad
15	<i>Hibiscus panduriformis</i> Burm.f.	Malvaceae		Irrigated fields- Soybean, Cotton.	O	Washim
16	<i>Malachra capitata</i> (L.) L.	Malvaceae	Ran-ambadi	Irrigated fields- Soybean, Tur, Cotton.	R	Sawarkhed
17	<i>Malvastrum coromandelianum</i> (L.) Garcke	Malvaceae	–	Irrigated fields- Soybean, Tur, Cotton.	C	Ladegaon
18	<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm.f.	Malvaceae	–	Irrigated fields- Soybean	C	Manora
19	<i>Sida cordata</i>	Malvaceae	–	Irrigated fields-	C	Umari Bk.

	(Burm.f.) Waalk.	Borss.			Soybean, Cotton.	Tur,	
20	<i>Sida spinosa</i> L.	Malvaceae	–		Irrigated fields- Soybean, Cotton.	Tur,	Umari Bk.
21	<i>Corchorus olitorius</i> L.	Tiliaceae	–		Unirrigated field		Amana
22	<i>Corchorus fascicularis</i> Lam.	Tiliaceae	Chichura		Irrigated fields- Soybean.		Rithad
23	<i>Corchorus trilocularis</i> L.	Tiliaceae	–		Irrigated fields- Soybean.		Dastapur
24	<i>Triumfetta pentandra</i> A. Rich.	Tiliaceae	–		Bunds of fields		Amana
25	<i>Triumfetta rotundifolia</i> Lam.	Tiliaceae	–		Bunds of fields		Washim
26	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> L.	Zygophyllaceae	Gokharu		Unirrigated fields		Manora
27	<i>Biophytum sensitivum</i> (L.) DC.	Oxalidaceae	Lajalu		Unirrigated fields		Sawargaon
28	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	Oxalidaceae	–		Irrigated fields- Soybean, Cotton.		Ladegaon
29	<i>Impatiens balsamina</i> L.	Balsaminaceae	Tiwadi		Irrigated fields- Soybean, Cotton		Washim
30	<i>Cissus vitiginea</i> L.	Vitaceae	–		Bunds of fields		Pimpalgaon
31	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Sapindaceae			Irrigated Field- Soybean		Karanja
32	<i>Alysicarpus bupleurifolius</i> (L.) DC.	Fabaceae	–		Irrigated field- Soybean, cotton, Tur.		Amana
33	<i>Alysicarpus longifolius</i> (Spreng.) Wight & Arn.	Fabaceae	Shevara		Irrigated field- Soybean, cotton, Tur.		Sakra
34	<i>Alysicarpus monilifer</i> (L.) DC.	Fabaceae	–		Unirrigated fields		Manora
35	<i>Alysicarpus ovalifolius</i> (Schum.) Leonard	Fabaceae	–		Unirrigated fields		Amana
36	<i>Alysicarpus procumbens</i> (Roxb.)	Fabaceae	–		Unirrigated fields		Sakra

	Schindl.					
37	<i>Alysicarpus vaginalis</i> (L.) DC.	Fabaceae	–	Unirrigated fields	C	Hiwara bk.
38	<i>Cajanus platycarpus</i> (Bth.)	Fabaceae	–	Unirrigated fields	C	Matoda
39	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.	Fabaceae	Gokarna	Unirrigated fields	C	Matoda
40	<i>Crotalaria retusa</i> L.	Fabaceae	–	Unirrigated fields	C	Jalalpur
41	<i>Crotalaria mysorensis</i> Roth	Fabaceae	–	Unirrigated fields	C	Risod
42	<i>Crotalaria orixensis</i> Willd.	Fabaceae	–	Unirrigated fields	C	Rithad
43	<i>Cullen corylifolia</i> (L.) Medik.	Fabaceae	Bawachi	Unirrigated fields	O	Umari Bk.
44	<i>Desmodium dichotomum</i> (Willd.) DC.	Fabaceae	Chikta	Bunds of fields	C	Sakra
45	<i>Gonigyna hirta</i> (Willd.) Ali	Fabaceae	—	Irrigated field-Soybean, Tur.	C	Wai pr. Karanja
46	<i>Indigofera cordifolia</i> Roth	Fabaceae	Godhadi	Irrigated field-Soybean.	C	Kolambi
47	<i>Indigofera glandulosa</i> Wendl.	Fabaceae	Barbada	Unirrigated fields	C	Wardari Kh.
48	<i>Indigofera linifolia</i> (L.f.) Retz.	Fabaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Washim
49	<i>Indigofera linnaei</i> Ali	Fabaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Dhamni manora
50	<i>Melilotus alba</i> Ledeb.	Fabaceae	—	Irrigated fields-Wheat, Chickpea	O	Poha
51	<i>Melilotus indica</i> (L.) All.	Fabaceae	Ran methi	Irrigated fields-Wheat, Chickpea	O	Poha
52	<i>Rhynchosia minima</i> (L.) DC.	Fabaceae	Turel	Irrigated field-Soybean, Tur.	C	Dhamni manors
53	<i>Rhynchosia minima</i> (L.) DC. Var. retroflexa	Fabaceae	–	Unirrigated Field	O	Ladegaon
54	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> (L) Pers.	Fabaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Lahi
55	<i>Tephrosia strigosa</i>	Fabaceae	—	Bunds of fields	O	Malegaon

	(Dalz.) Santapau & Maheshw.					
56	<i>Tephrosia villosa</i> (L.) Pers.	Fabaceae		Unirrigated fields	O	Manora
57	<i>Vigna trilobata</i> L.	Fabaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Dastapur
58	<i>Zornia gibbosa</i> Span.	Fabaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	
59	<i>Cassia mimosoides</i> L.	Caesalpiniaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Wardari kh.
60	<i>Cassia pumila</i> Lam.	Caesalpiniaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Wardari kh.
61	<i>Senna tora</i> (L.) Roxb.	Caesalpiniaceae	—	Bunds of fields	O	Wardari kh.
62	<i>Senna uniflora</i> L.	Caesalpiniaceae		Bunds of fields	O	Falegaon
63	<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Lythraceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Asola
64	<i>Rotala serpyllifolia</i> (Roth) Bremek.	Lythraceae	—	Bunds of fields	R	Washim
65	<i>Ludwigia perennis</i> L.	Onagraceae	Panlala wng	Bunds of fields	C	Khapardari
66	<i>Cucumis melo</i> L.	Cucurbitaceae	Shirni	Unirrigated fields	C	Hiwara Bk.
67	<i>Diplocyclos palmatus</i> (L.) C. Jeffrey	Cucurbitaceae	Shivlingi	Bunds of fields	C	Matoda
68	<i>Momordica cymbalaria</i> Hook.f.	Cucurbitaceae	Kadvanchi	Unirrigated fields	C	Khapardari
69	<i>Mukua maderaspatana</i> (L.) M. Roem.	Cucurbitaceae	—	Bunds of fields	O	Karanja
70	<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> L.	Aizoaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Asola
71	<i>Neanotis montholonii</i> (Hook.f.) Lewis	Rubiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	R	m.pir
72	<i>Spermacoce articularis</i> L.f.	Rubiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Wardari kh.
73	<i>Spermacoce pusilla</i> Wall.	Rubiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Risod
74	<i>Hedyotis aspera</i> B. Heyne ex Roth	Rubiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Amana
75	<i>Hedyotis corymbosa</i> L. (Lam)	Rubiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Supkhel
76	<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i> DC.	Rubiaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Khapardari
77	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Asteraceae	—	Unirrigated fields	A	Shivani D.

	(L.) L.					
78	<i>Bidens biternata</i> (Lour.) Merr. And sherff.	Asteraceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Pimpalgaon
79	<i>Blainvillea acmella</i> (L.) Philipson	Asteraceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Pimpalgaon
80	<i>Blumea lacera</i> (Burm.f.) DC.	Asteraceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Manora
81	<i>Blumea solidaginoides</i> (Poir.) DC.	Asteraceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Karanja
82	<i>Blumea membranacea</i> var. <i>gracilis</i> Hook.f.	Asteraceae	—	Bunds of fields	F	Karanja
83	<i>Caesulia axillaris</i> Roxb.	Asteraceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Washim
84	<i>Echinops echinatus</i> Roxb.	Asteraceae	—	Bunds of fields	O	Rithad
85	<i>Eclipta alba</i> (L.) Hassk.	Asteraceae	Maka	Irrigated fields-Soybean. Tur.	O	Pimpalgaon
86	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i> (L.) DC. ex DC.	Asteraceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Karanja
87	<i>Goniocaulon indicum</i> (Klein ex Willd.) Benth ex Clarke	Asteraceae	Karad kosla	Irrigated fields-Soybean	C	Sakra
88	<i>Grangea maderaspatana</i> (L.) Poir.	Asteraceae	—	Unirrigated fields	F	Risod
89	<i>Lagascea mollis</i> Cav.	Asteraceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Dhanora
90	<i>Launea procumbens</i> (Roxb.) Ramayya & Rajagopal	Asteraceae	Pathri	Unirrigated fields	C	Karanja
91	<i>Pentanema indicum</i> (L.) Ling	Asteraceae	Sonkadi	Unirrigated fields	C	Washim
92	<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	Asteraceae	Gajar gawat	Bunds of fields	A	Manoli
93	<i>Pulicaria angustifolia</i> DC.	Asteraceae	—	Bunds of fields	O	Washim
94	<i>Sonchus bracyotus</i>	Asteraceae	—	Irrigated fields-	R	Ladegaon

	DC.			Wheat, Chickpea.		
95	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> L.	Asteraceae	—	Irrigated fields- Wheat, Chickpea.	O	Karanja
96	<i>Spilanthes paniculata</i> Wall. Ex DC. Prodr.	Asteraceae	Pimpal Kawale	Unirrigated fields	C	Asola
97	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	Kambar modi	Unirrigated fields	A	Karli
98	<i>Vernonia cinerea</i> (L.) Less.	Asteraceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Sakra
99	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	Asteraceae	Zingurda	Unirrigated fields	O	Supkhel
100	<i>Zinnia peruviana</i> L.	Asteraceae	Ran Zendu	Unirrigated fields	O	Matoda
101	<i>Anagallis arvensis</i> var. <i>caerulea</i> (L.) Gouan	Primulaceae	—	Irrigated fields- Wheat, Chickpea.	C	Nainy
102	<i>Catharanthus pusillus</i> (Murr.) G. Don	Apocynaceae	Jangli sadafuli	Unirrigated fields	O	Amana
103	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> (Forssk.) Chiov.	Apocynaceae	Utran	Bunds of fields	O	Rithad
104	<i>Enicostema axillare</i> (Poir. ex Lam.) A. Raynal	Gentianaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Amana
105	<i>Exacum pedunculatum</i> L.	Gentianaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	F	Sakra
106	<i>Heliotropium ovalifolium</i> Forssk.	Boraginaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Risod
107	<i>Trichodesma indicum</i> (L.) Lehm.	Boraginaceae	Kachmada	Unirrigated fields	C	Sakhardoh
108	<i>Trichodesma zeylanicum</i> (Burm.f.) R.Br.	Boraginaceae	—	Bunds of fields	A	Sakra
109	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> L.	Convolvulaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Ladegaon
110	<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> (L.) L.	Convolvulaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Khapardari
111	<i>Ipomoea alba</i> L.	Convolvulaceae	—	Bunds of fields	O	Malegaon
112	<i>Ipomoea cairica</i> (L.)	Convolvulaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Koli

	Sweet					
113	<i>Ipomoea sinensis</i> (Desr.) Choisy	Convolvulaceae	—	Bunds of fields	F	Washim
114	<i>Ipomoea eriocarpa</i> R.Br.	Convolvulaceae	—	Irrigated fields	C	Falegaon
115	<i>Ipomoea hederifolia</i> L.	Convolvulaceae	Bopali	Unirrigated fields	O	Girda
116	<i>Ipomoea pestigris</i> (L.)	Convolvulaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Washim
117	<i>Ipomoea maxima</i> (L.f.) G.Don	Convolvulaceae		Unirrigated fields	C	Koli
118	<i>Merremia gangetica</i> (L.) Cufod.	Convolvulaceae	Kaliaphumari	Unirrigated fields	C	Washim
119	<i>Cuscuta chinensis</i> Lam.	Convolvulaceae	Adharvel	Unirrigated fields	C	Washim
120	<i>Physalis angulata</i> L.	Solanaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Kolar
121	<i>Physalis minima</i> L.	Solanaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	F	Falegaon
122	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	Solanaceae	Kamumi	Bunds of fields	C	Khapardari
123	<i>Datura ferox</i> L.	Solanaceae		Bunds of fields	O	Ladegaon
124	<i>Datura innoxia</i> Mill.	Solanaceae		Bunds of fields	A	Ladegaon
125	<i>Kickxia ramosissima</i> (Wall.) Janch.	Scrophulariaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Washim
126	<i>Stemodia viscosa</i> Roxb.	Scrophulariaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	F	Washim
127	<i>Striga angustifolia</i> (D.Don) C.J.Saldanha	Scrophulariaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Risod
128	<i>Verbascum chinense</i> (L.) Santapau	Scrophulariaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Risod
129	<i>Blepharis repens</i> (Vahl) Roth	Scrophulariaceae	Hadsan	Unirrigated fields	O	Nagzari
130	<i>Justicia diffusa</i> Willd.	Acanthaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Risod
131	<i>Justicia procumbens</i> L.	Acanthaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Asola
132	<i>Lepidagathis cristata</i> Willd.	Acanthaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Umari Bk.
133	<i>Dicliptera paniculata</i> (Forssk.) I.Darbysh.	Acanthaceae	—	Bunds of fields	O	Morgavhan
134	<i>Rostellularia japonica</i> (Thunb.) Ellis (Syn.)	Acanthaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Risod

	<i>Justicia japonica</i>)					
135	<i>Rungia elegans</i> Dalz. & Gibs.	Acanthaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Sakra
136	<i>Rungia pectinata</i> (L.) Nees	Acanthaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Sakhardoh
137	<i>Rungia repens</i> (L.) Nees	Acanthaceae	—	Bunds of fields	R	Rithad
138	<i>Anisomeles indica</i>	Lamiaceae	-----	Bunds of fields	O	Lahi
139	<i>Leonotis nepetifolia</i> (L.) R.Br.	Lamiaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Sawad
140	<i>Leucas urticifolia</i> (Vahl.) sm.	Lamiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Risod
141	<i>Leucas cephalotes</i> (Roxb.) Spreng.	Lamiaceae	—	Irrigated field-Soybean, Tur.	O	Sakhardoh
142	<i>Leucas martinicensis</i> (Jacq.)R.Br.Prodr.	Lamiaceae	—	Unirrigated field	O	Risod
143	<i>Ocimum americanum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	—	Unirrigated field	O	Sakhardoh
144	<i>Salvia plebeia</i> R.Br.	Lamiaceae	—	Unirrigated places	R	Washim
145	<i>Boerhaavia erecta</i> L.	Nyctaginaceae	Punarnava	Unirrigated places	O	Kamzara
146	<i>Boerhavia repens</i> Var. <i>diffusa</i> (L.) Hook.	Nyctaginaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Khirda
147	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Washim
148	<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L.) Juss.	Amaranthaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Karanja
149	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R.Br. ex DC.	Amaranthaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	A	Hiwara Bk.
150	<i>Amaranthus roxburghianus</i> Kunth.	Amaranthaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	F	M.pir
151	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Khapardari
152	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Hiwara Bk.
153	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Wardari kh.
154	<i>Digera muricata</i> (L.) Mart.	Amaranthaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	m.pir
155	<i>Gomphrena serrata</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Karanja

156	<i>Chenopodium album</i> L.	Chenopodiaceae		Irrigated fields- Wheat, Chickpea.	C	Wanoja
157	<i>Acalypha ciliata</i> Forssk.	Euphorbiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Amana
158	<i>Acalypha indica</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Manora
159	<i>Acalypha malabarica</i> Mull. Arg.	Euphorbiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Hiwara bk.
160	<i>Chrozophora rottleri</i> (Geis.) Juss. ex Spreng.	Euphorbiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Nainy
161	<i>Euphorbia geniculata</i> Ort.	Euphorbiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Manora
162	<i>Euphorbia heyneana</i> Spreng.	Euphorbiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	A	Nainy
163	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Karanja
164	<i>Euphorbia parviflora</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	—	Irrigated fields- Wheat, Chickpea.	C	Karanja
165	<i>Euphorbia dracunculoides</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Mangrulpir
166	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schum. & Thonn.	Phyllanthaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Karanja
167	<i>Phyllanthus maderaspatensis</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae	—	Irrigated fields- Soybean.	F	Supkhel
168	<i>Commelina axillaris</i> L.	Commelinaceae	—	Irrigated fields- Soybean.	C	Wardari kh.
169	<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Commelinaceae	—	Irrigated fields- Soybean.	O	Amana
170	<i>Commelina attenuate</i> Koen. ex vahl, Enum.	Commelinaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Wai pr.
171	<i>Tonningia axillaris</i> (L.) Raf.	Commelinaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Wardari kh.
172	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	—	Bunds of fields	O	Amana
173	<i>Apluda mutica</i> L.	Poaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Wardari Kkh.
174	<i>Aristida redacta</i> Stapf	Poaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Supkhel
175	<i>Arthraxon hispidus</i>	Poaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Wardari kh.

	(Thunb.) Makino					
176	<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	Poaceae	—	Cultivated fields	C	Amana
177	<i>Coix gigantia</i>	Poaceae	—	Bunds of fields	R	Falegaon
178	<i>Chrysopogon fulvus</i> (Spreng.) Chiov.	Poaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Girda
179	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	—	Irrigated fields	C	Manora
180	<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> (L.) Willd.	Poaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Karanja
181	<i>Dichanthium annulatum</i> (Forssk.) Stapf	Poaceae	—	Irrigated fields	C	Sakhardoh
182	<i>Dichanthium caricosum</i> (L.) A.Camus	Poaceae	—	Irrigated fields	C	Khapardari
183	<i>Dichanthium foveolatum</i> (Delile) Roberty	Poaceae	—	Irrigated fields	C	Washim
184	<i>Dichanthium pertusum</i> (L.) Clayton	Poaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Karanja
185	<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i> (Retz.) Koeler	Poaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	A	Manora
186	<i>Digitaria stricta</i> Roth	Poaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Dhamni Manora
187	<i>Dinebra retroflexa</i> (Vahl) Panz.	Poaceae	—	Irrigated fields	C	Sakhra
188	<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Poaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Washim
189	<i>Eragrostis aspera</i> (Jacq.) Nees	Poaceae	—	Irrigated fields	C	Manora
190	<i>Eragrostis ciliaris</i> (L.) R.Br.	Poaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Karanja
191	<i>Eragrostis japonica</i> (Thunb.) Trin.	Poaceae	—	Cultivated fields	C	Sakra
192	<i>Eragrostis pilosa</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Poaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	R	Kheda abai
193	<i>Eragrostis viscosa</i>	Poaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Vilegaon

	(Retz.) Trin.					
194	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> (L.) P. Beauv. ex Roem. & Schult.	Poaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Sawarkhed
195	<i>Heteropogon triticeus</i> (R.Br.) Stapf ex Craib	Poaceae	—	Bunds of fields	C	Washim
196	<i>Ischaemum pilosum</i> (Kl. ex Willd.) Wight	Poaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	C	Khapardari
197	<i>Melanocenchris jacquemontii</i> Jaub. & Spach	Poaceae	—	Irrigated fields	R	Washim
198	<i>Mnesithea granularis</i> (L.) Koning & Sosef	Poaceae	—	Unirrigated fields	O	Pimpalgaon
199	<i>Moorochloa eruciformis</i> (Sm.) Veldkamp	Poaceae	—	Irrigated fields	C	Karanja
200	<i>Ophiuros exaltatus</i> (L.) Kuntz.	Poaceae	—	Bunds of fields	A	Washim
201	<i>Panicum psilopodium</i> Trin.	Poaceae	—	Irrigated field	R	Washim
202	<i>Rottboellia cochinchinensis</i> (Lour.) Clayton	Poaceae	Itch grass	Bunds of fields	C	Sakra
203	<i>Setaria intermedia</i> Roem. & Schult.	Poaceae	Bristle grass	Bunds of fields	C	Pimpalgaon
204	<i>Setaria pumila</i> (Poir.) Roem. & Schult.	Poaceae	Yellow foxtail	Irrigated field	O	Amana
205	<i>Setaria verticillata</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Poaceae	Hooked bristle grass	Bunds of fields	O	Pimpalgaon
206	<i>Sporobolus coromandelianus</i> (Retz.) Kunth	Poaceae	—	Irrigated fields	C	Dhamni Manora
207	<i>Sporobolus indicus</i> (L.) R.Br.	Poaceae	Smut grass	Irrigated field	R	Karanja
208	<i>Themeda quadrivalvis</i> (L.) Kuntz.	Poaceae	Grader grass	Bunds of fields	C	Wardhari
209	<i>Urochloa panicoides</i>	Poaceae	Garden urochloa	Irrigated field	F	M.pir

	P. Beauv.					
210	<i>Urochloa ramosa</i> (L.) Nguyen	Poaceae	Dwarf urochloa	Irrigated field	O	Poha

Table 2. Photoplate of Weeds

<i>Malachra capitata</i> (L.) L.	<i>Corchorus fascicularis</i> Lam.

<p>GPS Map Camera Sakra, Maharashtra, India Mh Sh 209, Sakra, Maharashtra 444505, India Lat 20.165893° Long 77.224422° Sunday, 16/11/2025 11:24 AM GMT +05:30</p>	<p>GPS Map Camera Amana, Maharashtra, India 8wrq+rvh, Amana, Maharashtra 444503, India Lat 20.34207° Long 76.93923° 07/09/2025 11:42 AM GMT +05:30</p>
<p><i>Alysicarpus longifolius</i> (Spreng.) Wight & Arn.</p>	<p><i>Alysicarpus ovalifolius</i> (Schum.) Leonard</p>
<p>GPS Map Camera Sakra, Maharashtra, India Mh Sh 209, Sakra, Maharashtra 444505, India Lat 20.166096° Long 77.224562° Sunday, 16/11/2025 10:40 AM GMT +05:30</p>	<p>GPS Map Camera Wardari Kh., Maharashtra, India Hindu Hrudaysamrat Balasaheb Thackeray Maharashtra Samruddhi Mahamarg, Wardari Kh., Maharashtra 444503, India Lat 20.319943° Long 77.102417° 07/09/2025 09:49 AM GMT +05:30</p>
<p><i>Desmodium dichotomum</i> (Willd.) DC.</p>	<p><i>Indigofera glandulosa</i> Wendl.</p>

<p><i>Melilotus indica</i> (L.) All.</p>	<p><i>Ludwigia perennis</i> L.</p>
<p><i>Emilia sonchifolia</i> (L.) DC. ex DC.</p>	<p><i>Pentanema indicum</i> (L.) Ling</p>

<p>Ladegaon, Maharashtra, India Jgfa+ck, Ladegaon, Maharashtra 444110, India Lat 20.63068° Long 77.3393° Monday, 26/01/2026 02:14 PM GMT +05:30</p>	<p>Asola, Maharashtra, India Wmff+phv, Asola, Maharashtra 444506, India Lat 19.924132° Long 76.676261° Sunday, 16/11/2025 02:36 PM GMT +05:30</p>
<p><i>Sonchus bracyotus</i> DC.</p>	<p><i>Spilanthes paniculata</i> Wall. Ex DC. Prodr.</p>
<p>Amana, Maharashtra, India 8wrq+rvh, Amana, Maharashtra 444503, India Lat 20.341658° Long 76.939818° 07/09/2025 11:19 AM GMT +05:30</p>	<p>Ladegaon, Maharashtra, India Jgfa+ck, Ladegaon, Maharashtra 444110, India Lat 20.630684° Long 77.339366° Monday, 26/01/2026 02:34 PM GMT +05:30</p>
<p><i>Catharanthus pusillus</i> (Murr.) G. Don</p>	<p><i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> L.</p>

Result and Discussion

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The survey documented a total of 210 weed species representing 140 genera and 37 families. *Ipomoea* emerged as the most dominant genus, while Poaceae was the largest family, comprising 38 species. Distinct differences in weed composition were observed between unirrigated and irrigated agricultural fields. Unirrigated fields were predominantly infested with *Parthenium hysterophorus*, *Achyranthes aspera*, *Acalypha* sp., *Alternanthera sessilis*, *Xanthium strumarium*, *Boerhavia erecta*, *Euphorbia geniculate*, *Tridax Procumbens*, and *Phyllanthus* spp. In contrast, irrigated fields showed dominance of *Anagallis arvensis*, *Dinebra retroflexa*, *Melilotus alba*, *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Digera muricata*, *Eragrostis japonica*, *Moorochloa eruciformis*, *Launea procumbens*, and *Sonchus* spp. The observed variation in weed assemblages reflects the influence of irrigation practices on weed distribution. Overall, the results reveal substantial weed diversity in the agricultural landscapes of Washim District, and identification of dominant species under different field conditions provides valuable information for planning effective weed management strategies.

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